

Facile synthesis and copolymerization of methyl methacrylate with *N*-(4-chloro-2-nitro-phenyl)maleimide and characterization of the polymers

B. L. Hiran*, Rajesh Boriwal, S. N. Paliwal, Divya Singh, Champa Lal and Shivira Bapna

Chemical Kinetic and Polymer Research Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, M. L. Sukhadia University, Udaipur-313 001, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : hiranbl@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 22 December 2009, accepted 09 July 2010

Abstract : This work describes the synthesis, free radical polymerization and characterization of *N*-(4-chloro-2-nitro-phenyl)maleimide (CNPM) with methyl methacrylate (MMA). The free radical polymerization and copolymerization was carried out with azobis isobutyronitrile (AIBN) as an initiator in THF at 65 °C. Nine copolymer samples were prepared from different feed ratios of comonomer. Polymerization and copolymerization were also carried in different time and solvent-initiator system. The homo and copolymers were characterized by solubility, intrinsic viscosity, FT-IR and ¹H NMR spectral analysis. The thermal properties of homo and copolymer were studied by thermo gravimetric analysis (TGA). The initial decomposition temperature of copolymer was above 200 °C.

Keywords : *N*-(4-Chloro-2-nitro-phenyl)maleimide, AIBN, polymerization, TGA.

Introduction

Most aromatic polyimides produced by the thermal solid state phase imidization show insolubility and infusibility, which make processing difficult. These undesirable properties, which limit wider application of the polyimide's, are due to their chain rigidity as well as to poor defined molecular architectures¹⁻³. Polymers with defined architecte and controlled composition are of considerable interest for their academic and industrial uses⁴⁻⁶. Free radical copolymerizations have been shown that nearly alternating copolymerization took place, leading to copolymers with great structural stiffness and high thermal stability⁷. The maleimide based copolymers have been found to versatile applications in industries ranging from aerospace to the medical and micro electronics field^{8,9}. There have been many reports including patents on polymerization and copolymerization of *N*-substituted maleimide¹⁰⁻¹⁵. We report here the synthesis of monomer, *N*-(4-chloro-2-nitro-phenyl)maleimide and its homopolymerization and copolymerization with MMA. It was found that such copolymers have excellent thermal stability than the polymers of vinyl monomers. Studies of physical, spectral and thermal properties have been carried out in order to characterize the polymers. The effect

of different feed ratio of monomers on the properties of copolymers has been examined. The homo and copolymer also synthesized in different solvent-initiator and different time.

Results and discussion

The monomer *N*-(4-chloro-2-nitro-phenyl)maleimic acid **3** have been synthesized by the treatment of 4-chloro-2-nitroaniline with maleic anhydride. Which is confirmed by 3165–2689 cm⁻¹ owing to carboxylic -OH stretching as well as -NH stretching at 3315 cm⁻¹ in IR spectrum. Compound **3** reacts with P₂O₅ + H₂SO₄ after the cyclodehydration of acid into imide to give compound **4** *N*-(4-chloro-2-nitro-phenyl)maleimide. Synthesis of this compound is confirmed by the disappearance of both carboxylic acid and NH band in IR region and we get two new bands 1782, 1718 cm⁻¹ due to C=O functional group. Compound *N*-(4-chloro-2-nitro-phenyl)maleimide was refluxed for 48 h in the presence of AIBN in THF solvent to give homopolymer **5**. It shows C–C stretching at 1178 cm⁻¹ in IR and δ 3.3 CH of (-CH-CH)_n in ¹H NMR spectra. Compound *N*-(4-chloro-2-nitro-phenyl)maleimide upon further reflux for 48 h with methylmethacrylate in presence of AIBN in THF at 65 °C gives copolymer **7** of

compound 4 which shows C–O–C stretching at 1248 cm^{-1} in IR, δ 0.92 ppm due to CH_3 and δ 3.33 ppm due to OCH_3 of acrylate unit.

Solubility behaviour : The solubility of synthesized homo and copolymer samples was determined in polar and non polar solvents and has been summarized in Table 1. The homopolymer (H-CNPM) and copolymer (C-CNPM) are completely soluble in THF, DMF, ace-

Table 1. Solubility behavior of monomer, homopolymer and copolymer in polar and non polar solvents at $30\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

Solvent	CNPM	H-CNPM	C-CNPM
Ethyl alcohol	PS	S	S
Methyl alcohol	PS	S	S
Acetone	S	S	S
THF	S	S	S
DMF	S	S	S
DMSO	S	S	S
Ethyl acetate	S	PS	PS
Benzene	IS	IS	IS
1,4-Dioxane	S	S	S
Toluene	S	S	S
Cyclohexanone	S	S	S
Xylene	S	S	S
Chloroform	S	S	S
Carbon tetrachloride	IS	IS	IS

PS = Partially soluble, IS = Insoluble, S = Soluble.

tone, toluene, xylene, 1,4-dioxane and DMSO. The homopolymer and copolymer are insoluble in carbon tetrachloride. The solubility behavior of the homo and copolymer are depends on the composition of the polymer.

Intrinsic viscosity η :

Intrinsic viscosity η is a measure of hydromagnetic volume and depends on molecular weight, as well as on the size of the polymer coil in a given solution. The values of η in DMF solution at $30\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ are listed in Table 2. Intrinsic viscosity of homopolymer is lower than copolymer.

Table 2. Radical polymerization and copolymerization of H-CNPM with MMA in THF at $65\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

Polymer code	Feed mol fraction	Polymerization time (h)	Yield (%)	η (dl/g)	Appearance
H-CNPM	1.0	48	24.35	0.0415	Light orange
C-CNPM	0.5	48	34.55	0.0862	Orange

Thermal properties :

It is well known that polymaleimide is potential heat and chemical resistant; therefore maleimide is very useful for improving the polymeric properties. The thermograms were obtained by heating the homopolymer and copolymer samples in air ($10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$).

The results of percentage weight loss suffered from 200 to $600\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ at $100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ intervals are furnished in Table 3. The initial decomposition temperature T_i , temperature for maximum weight loss T_{max} and final decomposition temperature T_f are given in Table 4.

Table 3. Percentage weight loss of homo and copolymer at various temperatures from the TGA

Polymer code	200 $^\circ\text{C}$	300 $^\circ\text{C}$	400 $^\circ\text{C}$	500 $^\circ\text{C}$	550 $^\circ\text{C}$
H-CNPM	1.42	60.01	84.23	89.12	90.83
C-CNPM	7.58	71.15	85.69	89.99	90.89

Table 4. Thermal behavior of homo and copolymers

Polymer code	T_i ($^\circ\text{C}$)	T_{max} ($^\circ\text{C}$)	T_f ($^\circ\text{C}$)	Residue at 500 $^\circ\text{C}$ (%)
H-CNPM	220	400	550	11
C-CNPM	200	300	550	11

The results in Table 3 indicate that the relative thermal stability on the basis of T_i follows the order : H-CNPM > C-CNPM. The thermogram (Fig. 5) of H-CNPM shows the single step degradation. Initial degradation from $220\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ involving about 1.42%, $300\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $400\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $500\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $550\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ weight loss at 60.01%, 84.23%, 89.12% and 90.83%.

The thermogram (Fig. 6) of copolymer shows the step-by-step degradation. In copolymer initial weight degradation from C-CNPM $200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, involving about 7.58%, $350\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $400\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $500\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $550\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, weight loss at 71.15%, 85.69%, 89.99% and 90.89%.

Experimental

Materials :

Maleic anhydride was first recrystallized from chloroform and then further purified by sublimation at $50\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. 4-Chloro-2-nitro-aniline (LOBA, Pure), P_2O_5 and H_2SO_4 were used as received. MMA (SDF, AR) was shaken two to three times with 5% NaOH to eliminate hydroquinone

Fig. 1. IR spectra of H-CNPM

Fig. 2. IR spectra of C-CNPM.

inhibitor, dried over anhydrous CaCl_2 for 6 h and distilled¹⁶ AIBN (spectrochem) was recrystallized twice from methanol prior to use DMF, methanol, DMSO *etc.* used

in the present work were of analytical grade. THF was purified by distillation after being refluxed for 2 h in the presence of sodium¹⁶

Fig. 3. ^1H NMR spectra of H-CNPM.

Fig. 4. ^1H NMR spectra of C-CNPM.

Measurements :

^1H NMR spectra of monomer and polymer samples were taken in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ on a Bruker DPX-200/DPX-300

spectrometer at 200/300 MHz. The internal reference used was TMS. FT-IR spectra were taken in a Shimadzu 8201 PC ($4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$) FT-IR spectrometer, using KBr

Fig. 5. Thermogram of H-CNPM.

Fig. 6. Thermogram of C-CNPM.

pellet technique. The viscosity measurements Ubbelohde viscometer. The thermo grams in air were obtained on a Mettler TA-3000 system, at heating rate of 10 °C/min.

Method :

Synthesis of *N*-(4-chloro-2-nitro-phenyl)maleimide (CNPM) monomer has been prepared in two steps from maleic anhydride and 4-chloro-2-nitroaniline.

Synthesis of *N*-(4-Cl-2-NO₂-phenyl) maleimic acid (CNPMA) :

The solution of maleic anhydride (9.81 g, 0.1 mol) in DMF was gradually added over a period of 15 min to a well stirred solution of 4-chloro-2-nitroaniline (17.3 g,

0.1 mol) in DMF. The solution was stirred for 5 h at room temperature. The solution was poured into crushed ice. Orange precipitate of CNPMA was obtained. The precipitate was filtered and dried at 55 °C and then recrystallized from ethyl alcohol to obtain pure CNPMA in a 80% yield (m.p. 110 °C). The IR spectrum showed absorption bands at 3165–2689 (carboxylic acid O–H), 3315 (–NH), 825 (CH=CH), 672 cm⁻¹ (C–H bending).

Synthesis of *N*-(4-chloro-2-nitro-phenyl)maleimide (CNPM) :

N-(4-Chloro-2-nitro-phenyl)maleimic acid (0.1 mol)

in 70 ml DMF was taken in a flat round-bottomed flask. The solution was treated with concentrated H_2SO_4 and P_2O_5 . The whole solution was stirred for five hours. The resulting solution was poured in cooled water and orange precipitate was obtained. It was recrystallized from ethyl alcohol. Yield was 70% (m.p. 90 °C). The IR spectrum showed absorptions bands at 3178 (CH=CH), 2972 (C=C str.), 1782 -1718 (C=O str. five member imide ring), 1590-1445 (-C-NO₂ str.), 929 (C-Cl), 761 cm^{-1} (C=C str.); ¹H NMR (ppm) : 7.03 (-CH), 7.3-7.93 (m, Ar').

Polymerization :

Homopolymerization : *N*-(4-Chloro-2-nitro-phenyl)-maleimide (2.25 g for 0.01 mol) and 40 ml THF were taken in a flat round-bottomed flask and the initiator AIBN was added. The solution was refluxed for 48 h at 65 °C. The homopolymer was isolated by using an excess quantity of methanol water-mixture. The crude H-CNPM was purified by dissolving it in THF and precipitating from a methanol-water mixture. It was dried under vacuum at 60 °C. The homopolymerization was carried out for diffe-

rent time and the yields are given in Table 5. Percentage yield of homopolymer in various solvent-initiator systems are given in Table 6; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3165 (Ar-H), 1761, 1735 (C=O), 1595–1490 (NO_2), 1375 (C–N), 1178 (C–C), 878 (C–Cl); ^1H NMR δ (ppm) : 3.3 (–CH), 7.0–8.2 (m, Ar’).

purify the copolymer sample. The precipitated copolymer was washed with methanol for several times and dried at 60 °C under vacuum. The copolymer sample was prepared using different feed ratio of comonomers are given in Table 7. Copolymerization was carried out for different time and yield are given in Table 5. Percentage yield

Table 5. Effect of time on yield of homo and copolymer

Polymer code	18 h	24 h	30 h	36 h	48 h	54 h	60 h
H-CNPM	15.20%	20.12%	22.58%	27.19%	29.38%	31.80%	32.20%
C-CNPM	43.60	48.10	52.50	57.90	59.30	60.10	60.80

Table 6. Percentage yield of homopolymer and copolymer in various solvent initiator systems

Solvent	AIBN		BPO	
	H-CNPM	C-CNPM	H-CNPM	C-CNPM
	% yield	% yield	% yield	% yield
THF	29.38	59.30	29.01	58.25
DMF	19.12	38.10	17.22	32.10
Acetone	16.52	35.20	16.05	31.27
Ethyl acetate	15.20	30.12	14.51	27.10
1,4-Dioxane	25.61	28.20	24.82	25.63

Copolymerization : The copolymerization was carried out at 65 °C for 18, 24, 30, 36, 48, 54 h employing equimolar amount of comonomers MMA and CNPM in 40 ml THF with 0.25 mg AIBN. The copolymer was isolated from an excess quantity of methanol containing water. After dissolving the crude copolymer in THF, it was precipitated from an excess quantity of methanol-water mixture. The process was repeated three times to

of copolymer in various solvent-initiator systems are given in Table 6; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3134 (Ar-H), 1751, 1727 (C=O), 1447–1508 (NO_2), 1342 (C–N), 1248 (C–O–C), 1150 (C–C), 822 (C–Cl); ^1H NMR δ (ppm) : 2.7–2.9 (–CH), 7.0–8.3 (m, Ar’), 0.92 (CH_3), 1.7–1.8 (CH_2), 3.3 (OCH_3).

Conclusion :

Homopolymerization and copolymerization proceed through the free radical mechanism. The most suitable initiator-solvent pair for the homo and copolymerization was found to be AIBN-THF. The investigated homo and copolymaleimides show excellent solubility in THF, DMF, acetone, toluene, xylene, 1,4-dioxane and DMSO. The homo and copolymer were characterized by IR and ^1H NMR spectral analysis. Synthesized homopolymer show good thermal stability than copolymer but other properties are improved in copolymerization.

Table 7. Radical polymerization and copolymerization of N-CNPM and MMA in THF at 65 °C

Polymer code	Feed ratios CNPM : MMA	Polymer time (h)	Yield (%)	State	Appearance
CNPM-1	1 : 9	48	49.79	Viscous solid	Light orange
CNPM-2	2 : 8	48	45.19	Viscous solid	Light orange
CNPM-3	3 : 7	48	40.20	Viscous solid	Light orange
CNPM-4	4 : 6	48	36.18	Solid	Orange
CNPM-5	5 : 5	48	34.55	Solid	Orange
CNPM-6	6 : 4	48	32.20	Solid	Orange
CNPM-7	7 : 3	48	30.12	Solid	Orange
CNPM-8	8 : 2	48	27.06	Solid	Orange
CNPM-9	9 : 1	48	25.16	Solid	Orange
H-CNPM-10	10 : 0	48	24.35	Solid	Light orange

Acknowledgement

We are thankful to CDRI, Lucknow and SICART, Vallabh Vidyanagar for analysis work.

References

1. R. C. P. Cubbon, *Polymer*, 1965, **6**, 419.
2. J. Barrates-Rienda, Gonzalez De La, J. L. Camp and Ramos Gonazalez, *J. Macromol. Sci. Chem.*, 1997, **A11**, 267.
3. Kagawak, T. Oishi, K. Matsusaki and Fujimotom, *Polymer*, 1995, **36**, 941.
4. E. Rizzardo and G. J. C. Moad, (ed.), CRC, Boca Raton, FL, 1996, **5**, 3834.
5. K. Rizzardo Matyjaszewski, *ACS Symp. Ser.*, 1998, **685**, 2.
6. H. M. Li and S. A. Lin, *J. Macromol. Sci., Pure Appl. Chem.*, 2007, **A37**, 1475.
7. C. E. Scroog, *Polyimides J. Poly. Sci.*, 1976, **11**, 161.
8. L. Takao, N. Tsutomu, F. Wakichi and T. Magao, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 1996, **60**, 37.
9. J. Y. Chang, T. J. Kim and M. J. Han, *Polymer*, 1997, **38**, 4651.
10. J. Coleman and J. Conrady, *J. Polym. Sci.*, 1959, **38**, 241.
11. B. L. Hiran, J. Chaudhary, S. N. Paliwal and P. R. Choudhary, *E. Journal of Chemistry*, 2007, **4**, 265.
12. B. L. Hiran and S. N. Paliwal, *Malaysian Polymer Journal*, 2008, **2**, 1.
13. B. L. Hiran, R. Boriwal, S. Bapana and S. N. Paliwal, *J. Chemical Technology and Metallurgy*, 2010, **45**, 127.
14. S. L. Oswal, N. S. Sarkar, V. K. Bhandari, H. B. Oza and C. B. Patel, *Iranian Polymer Journal*, 2007, **13**, 297.
15. C. P. R. Nair, *J. Polym. Sci., Polym. Chem. Ed.*, 1992, **26**, 47.
16. V. Choudhary and D. S. Varma, *J. Therm. Anal.*, 1993, **39**, 633.